

Screen-printed electrodes for glucose using non-conducting polymers and electron mediator

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This paper deals with the performance of amperometric glucose biosensor on two aspects, namely, use of non-conducting polymers and electron transfer mediator. The proposed method of using number of non conducting polymers for immobilization of enzymes on the surface of an amperometric electrode shows that the performance varies greatly with the type of polymer used. The use of a suitable electron mediator (TBF-TCNQ) also shows a great improvement on performance over the conventional glucose sensors.

Detection of biological analyte has gained considerable interest in the development of biosensors based on the entrapment of enzymes at an electrochemical interface in amperometric biosensor¹. Perhaps the most successful type of biosensor is the amperometric glucose biosensor. The immobilization of the redox enzyme, glucose oxidase (GOD) on an amperometric enzyme electrode has proved important, providing a relevant model system for fundamental research, as well as a diagnostic tool for the rapid detection of glucose. Interestingly, however, there has been only limited work reported which has attempted to quantify any variations in the amounts of enzyme entrapped in the polymer film as binder. The application of electron mediator TBF-TCNQ on the performance of the glucose sensor was also studied.

Results and Discussion

Performance of electrodes with various polymers as immobilization agents :

Fig. 1 shows a comparative study on the performances of glucose electrodes using various polymers for immobilization of GOD on the working electrode surface. The polymeric or nonpolymeric binders were nafion, poly-L-lysine, glutaraldehyde and polyethyleneimine (PEI). The figure reveals that nafion is the most efficient binder for glucose immobilization. For the GOD electrodes immobilized with poly-L-lysine, glutaraldehyde and PEI, the increase in current up to 15 mM concentration of glucose solution was insignificant. In all these cases, a straight-line correlation could be made for a wide range of concentration.

Performance of GOD electrode with electron transfer mediator TBF-TCNQ :

In this experiment the electrodes with GOD activities of

Fig. 1. Comparison of performance of GOD electrodes using various polymers for immobilizing the enzyme (applied potential 0.35 V vs WE, current reading is average of three different experiments).

Fig. 2. Performance of glucose biosensors TBF-TCNQ electron transfer mediator (applied potential 0.4 V vs WE, current reading is average of three different experiments).

Note

300 and 400 mU were used with and without electron transfer mediator to see the effect on response. The concentration of glucose used was in the range of 0–80 mM. The results are depicted in Fig. 2. The electrodes with mediator showed better result compared to the electrodes without mediator in both the enzyme concentrations, i.e. 300 and 400 mU.

Experimental

A buffer of 0.2 M Na₂HPO₄-NaH₂PO₄ (pH 7.4) containing 0.1 M KCl was used². Glucose oxidase (GOD, EC 1.1.3.4, *Aspergillus niger*, specific activity 0.31 U g⁻¹), glucose, polyethyleneimine (PEI), and glutaraldehyde (Sigma), nafion (Aldrich), stabilguard (Sur Modics), poly-L-lysine (Sigma), tetrabutylammonium tetrafluoroborate (TBF) (Fluka) and tetracyanoquinodimethane (TCNQ) (Sigma) were used. All buffers were prepared with double-distilled water.

An AutoLab electrochemical analyzer (μ AutoLab-Type II) with GPES software (Ecochemie, Utrecht, The Netherlands) was used for measurements. The average value of three readings was used for analysis of results. Three-electrode devices were prepared in-house by a screen-printing process using a DEK 248 machine (DEK, Weymouth, UK). Devices were printed on to 250 μ m thick polyester sheet (Cadillac Plastic). The sensor consisted of a working electrode made of rhodinized carbon, a Ag/AgCl reference electrode and a counter electrode made of carbon. After printing, the electrodes were heat-treated for curing the epoxy resin nonconducting cover for 2 h at 120^o3.

Immobilization of GOD with nafion, poly-L-lysine, glutaraldehyde, PEI : Aliquots (10 μ L) with various strengths of GOD in 2% glutaraldehyde or 1.5% PEI or 0.1% poly-L-lysine, 25% nafion in PBS were inoculated on each WE, dried at 4^o and washed in PBS and stored at 4^o in air until required.

GOD electrodes with electron transfer mediator : Aliquots (10 μ L) of GOD solution in PBS with different strengths were inoculated on each WE and dried. Aliquots (10 μ L) containing 0.5% TBF and 0.5% TCNQ in tetrahydrofuran (THF) were pipetted onto each WE containing GOD and dried. Aliquots (10 μ L) with 2% glutaraldehyde and stabilguard in PBS were inoculated on each WE, dried and washed in PBS and stored at 4^o.

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References

1. A. P. F. Turner, I. Karube and G. S. Wilson, "Biosensors, Fundamentals and Applications", Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1987.
2. "Data for Biochemical Research", 3rd. ed., eds. M. C. Dawson, D. C. Elliott, W. H. Elliot and K. M. Jones, Clarendon, Oxford, 1984.
3. P. Sarkar, *Microchem. J.*, 2000, **64**, 283.